

Obtaining the Tsallis Distribution from Complex Integration with Poles

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B Feb. 11, 2025

In a previous note (1), we suggested that the Tsallis $\ln_q(x) = \{x^{\text{power}(1-q) - 1}\}/(1-q)$ function arises from two body elastic scattering. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one has $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$, while in the Tsallis case (and the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases), the latter is replaced with $G(f(e_1)) G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3)) G(f(e_4))$. In the Tsallis case one has the additional q parameter so $G(f(e_i))$ is really $G(f(-e_i/T, q))$.

If one imagines a general $G(f(e_i, q))$ such that $q=1$ yields $G(f) = f$ (the MB case), one may consider the generalized information $\ln(G(f, q))$ as well as its d/dq derivative. In such a case, $d/dq \ln(G(f, q)) = \text{Function}(e/T, q)$, where $G(f)$ is in the form of an exponential and Function is the d/dq derivative of its argument. We suggest that if one considers poles arising in $\text{Function}(e/T, q)$ from $q-1$, the simplest pole form (with both residues contributing values proportional to $-e/t$) leads to the Tsallis distribution: $f_q = Cq \{ 1 - (1-q) e/T \}^{\text{power}(1/(1-q))}$.

Two Body Elastic Scattering

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, $C \exp(-e_i/T)$, may be obtained from two body time reversal balanced elastic scattering:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1b))$$

Taking \ln of ((1b)) and equating with ((1a)) multiplied by $-1/T$ yields:

$$\ln(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((2))$$

One may generalize ((1b)) (as in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases) (see (1)) to:

$$G(f(e_1)) G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3)) G(f(e_4)) \quad ((3))$$

In (1), we suggested that one may consider the Tsallis case as being represented by a $G(f(e_i, q))$ such that:

$$\ln(G(f)) = \ln_q(f) \quad \text{where:} \quad \ln_q x = \{ x^{\text{power}(1-q) - 1} \} / (1-q) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{If } q=1, \ln_q x = \ln(x) \quad ((5))$$

The Tsallis distribution is:

$$\text{Exp}_q x = Cq \{ 1 + (1-q) x \}^{\text{power}(1/(1-q))} \quad ((6))$$

If one were simply to take d/dq of the Tsallis distribution ((6)), given that it is a power law, one may express the RHS as a regular exponential function. Then:

$$d/dq f(e,q) = f(e,q) \text{ Function}(e/T, q) \text{ or } d/dq \ln(f(e/T,q)) = \text{Function}(e/T, q) \quad ((7))$$

In other words the idea of an $\ln(G(f))$ appears in $\ln(f(e/T,q))$ even if one does not consider two body elastic scattering.

Obtaining the Tsallis Distribution from d/dq of $\ln(G(f))$ with $1-q$ Poles

We suggest as a starting point, trying to obtain the Tsallis distribution from:

$$d/dq \ln(G(f(e/T, q))) = \text{FunctionA}(e/T, q) \text{ where FunctionA is unknown} \quad ((8))$$

For $q=1$, $G(f)=f$. We suggest that the form $d/dq \ln(G(f))$ arises from G being written in the form of an exponential because $d/dq \exp(B(f(e/T,q)))$ yields $\exp(B(f)) * d/dq B(e/T, q)$. ((9))

We suggest that one bring dq from the LHS of ((8)) to the RHS and use pole integration with $1-q$ being the variable of interest.

We seek the simplest pole function which will achieve this result.

d/dq of the argument of the exponential must bring back a pole in $1-q$ or poles. We consider the simplest forms which achieve this.

One scenario is: $\exp(\ln(1-q))$ because $d/dq (\exp(\ln(1-q))) = \exp(\ln(1-q)) (-1/(1-q))$ ((10))
One may note, however, that $\exp(\ln(1-q)) = 1-q$ and so such a term would yield a 0 in the denominator when setting $q=1$ and so we reject this scenario.

A second scenario is to have a $1/(1-q)$ pole type term already in the argument of the exponential, i.e.:

$$\ln(G(f)) = \exp(1/(1-q) \text{ function4}((1-q), e/T)) \quad ((11)) \text{ where function4 is unknown}$$

Taking d/dq of the argument of $\exp()$ in ((11)) yields:

$$1/\{ (1-q)(1-q) \} \text{ function4}((1-q), e/T) + 1/(1-q) d/dq \text{ function4} \quad ((12))$$

Thus, function4 must contain $(1-q)$. The simplest expression is one with $(1-q)$ appearing to power 1. Given that $\int d \ln(G(f)) = -e/T$, when integrating by dq over the pole $q=1$, one must obtain $-e/T$ as well. This implies that one has a term of the form

$$-(1-q) e/T \quad ((13))$$

In pole integration $\int Fa(1-q) dq / \{ (1-q)(1-q) \}$ means that the derivative dFa/dq is not zero in order to obtain a nonzero result. If ((13)) appears, one picks up: $(-e/T)$.

There is, however, a second term in ((12)) which is a single pole. If function4 contains $(1-q)^{-e/T}$, and actually appears as $(1-q)^{-e/T}$ then d/dq function4 removes q dependence and one obtains 0 from this second term. To prevent this and have both terms contribute, the simplest form for function4 is:

$$\ln(1 - (1-q)^{-e/T}) \quad ((14))$$

In such a case, both terms in ((12)) contribute residues proportional to $-e/T$ when $q=1$ which matches : $\text{Integral } d \ln G(f(q=1), e) = \ln(f(e))$.

Thus, one concludes that:

$$f(e, q) = Cq \exp(1/(1-q) \ln(1 - (1-q)^{-e/T})) \text{ or } f(e, q) = Cq \{ 1 + (1-q)^{-e/T} \}^{\text{power } (1/(1-q))} \quad ((15))$$

We suggest that one may obtain the Tsallis distribution by seeking the simplest $1-q$ pole structure in an exponential function such that both terms of $d/dq \exp(1/(1-q) \text{Function}(1-q, -e/T))$ contribute residues, where $\text{Function}(1-q)$ does not contain a pole in $1-q$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $\ln(f(e_i/T)) = -e_i/T$ for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case and that $\ln(G(f)) = -e_i/T$ for the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, ie. a generalization $G(f)$ appears instead of f . We use this result and suggest that the Tsallis case follows: $\ln(G(f(e_i/T, q))) = -e_i/T$. We then consider $d/dq \ln(G(f)) = \text{function}((1-q), -e_i/T)$ which we suggest has poles in $1-q$ so one may bring dq over to the RHS and integrate over the poles to obtain residues proportional to $-e_i/T$. $\text{Integral } d \ln(G(f(q))) = \ln(G(f)) = \ln f$ for $q=1$. We seek the simplest pole structure in $\text{function}(1-q)$. First, we note that $d/dq \ln(G(f)) = dG/dq / G$, so one seeks the distribution $G(f)$ as an exponential. $\text{function}(1-q)$ is then d/dq of the argument of the exponential in the unnormalized case. In order to obtain the simplest pole structure, we suggest a $1/(1-q)$ pole existing in the argument of the exponential, i.e. $1/(1-q) \text{function}((1-q), -e/T)$. Taking d/dq leads to two terms, one in $1/\{(1-q)(1-q)\}$, the other in $1/(1-q)$. If one wishes both to contribute residues proportional to $-e_i/T$, then function is $1 - (1-q)^{-e/T}$. This result, however, yields the Tsallis distribution: $f(e_i/T, q) = \{ 1 + (1-q)^{-e/T} \}^{\text{power } (1/(1-q))}$.

References

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